

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“FROM COLLEGE DREAMS TO TEACHING HOSPITALITY”

I had big dreams, as I pursued college.
Beneath clear skies obtained a hospitality degree,
Hereinafter, the nearby hotel's first role began,
To master the art of grace heartily.

From nearby shores to far-off locations,
Through seas, in competent hands.
I honed my skills in hotels abroad,
Wherein souls and traditions blend.

Such hallowed halls of learning,
A vibrant mentor, discernment in their grasp,
I ignite thoughts, share wisdom,
Mold destinies brimming with enthusiasm.

I obtained a master's degree with passion,
The excellency of yours at a learning process.
Staying up late,
Pursuing aspirations where minds come alive.

The Ph.D. road, a quest to learn,
It's a tough journey, I see.
To study, teach, and light the way,
With learning's spark, ambitions sway.

From student days to teacher's role,
A journey from darkness to light.
I mentor students who possess great intelligence.
Building futures that will last.

Each class, each lesson that I share,
Leaves traces of my time and care.
The heart of service, I pass on,
As students grow from dusk to dawn.

